

Kinetics and Mechanism of Oxidative Decarboxylation and Deamination of Amino Acids by *N*-Chloro-*N*-sodio-*p*-toluenesulphonamide at Low Acid Concentrations

B. THIMME GOWDA* and B. S. SHERIGARA

Department of Post-Graduate Studies & Research in Chemistry, Mangalore University, Mangalagangothri-574 199

Manuscript received 21 November 1985, revised 4 June 1986, accepted 17 February 1987

Kinetics of oxidation of seven amino acids by chloramine-T has been investigated in low acid medium. The rate followed first order kinetics in [CAT] and zero order each in [amino acid] and $[H^+]$. Effect of added reaction product, *p*-toluenesulphonamide and variation of ionic strength and dielectric constant of the reaction medium on the rate have also been investigated. Activation parameters have been computed from the Arrhenius plots. Suitable mechanism has been proposed to account for the observed kinetics.

CHLORAMINE-T (CAT), an organic *N*-halogeno-*N*-metallo reagent has been used for oxidation of amino acids¹⁻³ in both acidic and alkaline media. It is a source of Cl^+ , hypochlorite and *N*-anion which act both as base and nucleophile. CAT interacts with a wide range of functional groups both as a chlorinating agent and an oxidising agent in aqueous and partially aqueous media in the presence of acids or alkalies^{4,5}. It undergoes a two-electron change in its reactions, the products being *p*-toluenesulphonamide (PTS) and sodium chloride. The redox potential of CAT-PTS is pH-dependent and decreases with the increase in pH of the medium (E_{redox} 1.14, 0.78, 0.61 and 0.5 V at pH 0.65, 7.0, 9.7 and 12, respectively). Hence, depending upon the pH of the medium, CAT (RNCINa, where $R=CH_2C_6H_4SO_2$) furnishes different types of reactive species in solution^{4,5}. *N*-Chloro-*p*-toluenesulphonamide (monochloramine-T, RNHCl), dichloramine-T ($RNCl_2$) and HOCl are the probable reactive species in acid solution in the absence of Cl^- and Cl_2 in the presence of Cl^- . $RNCl^-$ and OCI^- are the predominant species in alkaline solution. Although there are a number of reports on the kinetics of oxidations by CAT in acid medium, these investigations have been carried out with $[H^+] > 0.01 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$. We thought it worthwhile to investigate CAT kinetics in very low acid medium ($0.001-0.01 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$) as the oxidant interacts with the substrates in different forms under different reaction conditions. The object was to generalise the mechanism of CAT reactions. We report herein the results of our studies using amino acids as substrates.

Experimental

Aqueous stock solution of chloramine-T (Fluka, A.G.) was standardised iodometrically and stored

in dark coloured bottles. The amino acids selected were L-glycine (Gly), L-valine (Val), L-serine (Ser), L-threonine (Thr), L-arginine (Arg), L-histidine (His) and L-glutamine (Gln). Chromatographically pure amino acids (Sisco Research Laboratories, India) were used and their aqueous stock solutions were standardised. Preliminary investigations showed that the ionic strength of the medium has no significant effect on the reaction rate with all the amino acids.

The kinetic studies were made in glass-stoppered pyrex boiling tubes whose outer surfaces were coated black to eliminate photochemical effects. The reactions were initiated by the rapid addition of known quantities of CAT solutions, thermally equilibrated at a desired temperature, to mixtures of appropriate amounts of the amino acid, $HClO_2$ and water (to keep the total volume constant) in the boiling tubes, pre-equilibrated at the same temperature. The progress of the reaction was monitored by iodometric estimation of unreacted oxidant at regular intervals of time. The reaction was followed for nearly two half-lives under pseudo-first order conditions with [amino acid] always greater than [CAT] at least by 5-10 times. The pseudo-first order rate constants computed by the method of least-squares were reproducible within $\pm 4\%$.

Stoichiometry and product analysis : The stoichiometry of amino acid-CAT reactions were determined under substrate excess conditions by thermally equilibrating various ratios of [amino acid] to [CAT] at different $[H^+]$ ($0.001-0.01 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$) at 303 K for 24 h. The reaction products were identified to be ammonia, carbon dioxide, and the corresponding aldehyde by standard tests. PTS, the reduced product of the oxidant, was detected by paper chromatography with benzyl alcohol

saturated with water as the solvent and 0.5% vanillin in 1% HCl solution in ether as the spray reagent (R_f 0.91). The observed stoichiometry may be represented by equation (1).

where, R' = H (Gly), $(\text{CH}_2)_2\text{CH}$ (Val), CH_2OH (Ser), CH_2CHOH (Thr), $\text{H}_2\text{NC(NH)NH(CH}_2\text{)}_2$ (Arg), $\text{HC} \begin{array}{l} \text{N} \\ \text{C} \\ \text{NH} \end{array} \begin{array}{l} \text{---} \\ \text{---} \\ \text{---} \end{array} \begin{array}{l} \text{---} \\ \text{---} \\ \text{---} \end{array} \text{CH}_2$ (His) and H_2NCOCH_2 (Gln).

Results

Kinetics of reactions of amino acids with CAT in perchloric acid medium were investigated at several initial concentrations of the reactants (Tables 1 and 2). At constant [acid] and with amino acid in excess, plots of $\log [\text{CAT}]_0/[\text{CAT}]$ vs time were linear at least upto 65% completion of reaction showing first order kinetics in [CAT] (Table 1). The rates were unaffected by the changes in either [amino acid] or $[\text{HClO}_4]$ indicating zero order dependence of rate on them, which was contrary to the observed first order in [amino acid] and inverse first order in $[\text{H}^+]$ at $[\text{H}^+] > 0.01 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$. The pH of the reaction mixtures measured as [amino acid] and $[\text{HClO}_4]$ were varied (Table 3). Variations of ionic strength of the medium and addition of the reaction products PTS and Cl^- had no significant effect on the rate. Generally, the change of solvent composition of the medium had little effect on the rate. The activation parameters have been computed from the Arrhenius plots by measuring rates at different temperatures (293–318 K) (Table 4).

Discussion

Chloramine-T (sodium salt of *N*-chloro-*p*-toluenesulphonamide) is fairly a strong electrolyte in aqueous solutions^{3,4,5}. The following equilibria exist in its aqueous solutions,

Therefore, the probable oxidising species in CAT solutions at low acid conditions are RNCl^- , RNHCl , RNCl_2 , HOCl and OCl^- . If RNCl_2 were to be the reactive species one could expect second order dependence of rate on [CAT] which is contrary to the experimental observations. Further, Bishop and Jennings⁴, as a first approximation have calculated the concentrations of various species present in 0.05 M CAT solutions at different pH (Table 5). As can be seen from Table 5, RNHCl is the predominant species upto pH ~ 2.5 and $[\text{RNCl}^-]$ is increasing with increase in pH and becomes the predominant species after pH ≈ 2.5 . In the present investigation, the reactions of all the amino acids with CAT have been studied in a medium with pH > 2.5 (Table 3). Therefore, under these experimental conditions, RNCl^- is the predominant and reactive species.

The amino acids exist in different forms in aqueous solutions⁶. They exist mostly in the

TABLE 1—EFFECT OF THE [REACTANT] AND $[\text{HClO}_4]$ ON THE RATE OF REACTION AT 308 K

[CAT] $\times 10^3 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$	[A.A] $\times 10^3 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$	[HClO ₄] ¹ $\times 10^3 \text{ mol dm}^{-3}$	$k_{\text{obs}} \times 10^4 \text{ s}^{-1}$						
			Gly	Val	Ser	Thr	Arg	His	Gln
2.0 ^a	1.0	5.0	13.5	9.34	10.6	4.8	6.77	11.4	14.3
2.0 ^a	2.0	5.0	16.5	9.45	12.6	4.8	6.9	11.6	14.5
2.0 ^a	3.0	5.0	16.4	9.44	12.5	4.6	6.92	11.7	14.3
2.0 ^a	5.0	5.0	16.3	9.45	12.5	4.55	6.90	11.8	14.3
2.0 ^a	6.0	5.0	16.3	9.48	12.2	4.6	6.98	11.8	14.2
2.0 ^a	8.0	5.0	16.4	9.0	12.4	4.35	7.01	12.0	14.5
2.0 ^a	10.0	5.0	16.7	8.5	12.5	4.7	7.25	—	14.1
0.5	2.0 ^b	5.0	—	—	11.9	4.7	7.04	12.1	—
1.0	2.0 ^b	5.0	12.1	9.2	12.2	4.8	7.0	11.9	14.0
2.0	2.0 ^b	5.0	18.0	9.5	12.6	4.8	6.9	11.6	14.3
4.0	2.0 ^b	5.0	16.3	9.5	12.8	4.8	6.95	12.0	14.6
6.0	2.0 ^b	5.0	16.5	9.7	13.0	4.9	7.21	12.1	14.7
2.0 ^a	2.0 ^b	1.0	16.0	—	13.0	4.09	6.29	8.85	14.0
2.0 ^a	2.0 ^b	2.0	16.3	—	12.9	4.3	6.58	10.2	14.3
2.0 ^a	2.0 ^b	4.0	16.3	9.1	12.6	4.6	6.78	11.0	14.6
2.0 ^a	2.0 ^b	5.0	16.3	9.5	12.6	4.8	6.9	11.5	14.3
2.0 ^a	2.0 ^b	6.0	16.3	10.1	12.6	4.6	6.86	12.6	14.5
2.0 ^a	2.0 ^b	8.0	16.5	10.5	12.0	4.4	6.97	12.3	14.7
2.0 ^a	2.0 ^b	10.0	17.0	11.8	11.5	4.6	6.97	11.8	14.9

^aWith all the amino acids except Gly and Val, 4.0 (Gly) and 5.0 (Val), 5.0 (Val) and 3.0 (Gln).

^bWith Ser, Thr, Arg and His, and 6.0 (Gly),

TABLE 2—EFFECT OF ADDED PRODUCT, [PTS], TEMPERATURE, DIELECTRIC CONSTANT (D) AND IONIC STRENGTH (μ) OF THE MEDIUM ON REACTION RATE*

[PTS] $\times 10^3$ mol dm ⁻³	$k_{obs} \times 10^4$ s ⁻¹						
	Gly	Val	Ser	Thr	Arg	His	Gln
1.0	16.4	9.45	12.6	4.75	6.9	11.6	14.8
2.0	16.5	9.84	12.65	4.40	6.9	11.8	14.6
4.0	16.35	9.28	12.55	4.30	6.87	12.0	14.9
8.0	16.45	9.80	12.6	4.25	6.85	12.2	14.8
Temp (K)							
298	8.02	4.2	6.4	1.82	1.82	2.56	6.2
303	16.28	9.5	12.6	4.8	6.9	11.5	14.9
308	18.88	11.1	15.4	5.8	14.6	18.84	24.8
315	26.11	16.5	22.8	12.8	29.9	48.0	35.8
318	38.98	24.0	32.9	20.6	54.4	98.7	45.2
D							
76.58	16.3	9.5	12.6	4.8	6.9	11.5	14.8
72.09	16.1	8.8	11.5	3.95	7.7	10.8	14.0
67.60	14.8	7.4	11.0	3.02	10.3	12.7	13.5
63.10	13.8	6.9	9.6	2.95	11.0	16.2	13.2
60.86	—	6.5	—	—	—	—	—
58.60	12.9	—	9.0	2.36	11.5	21.9	12.8
μ (mol dm ⁻³)							
0.2	16.4	9.35	12.5	4.8	6.9	11.6	14.4
0.5	16.5	9.5	12.6	4.75	6.9	11.7	14.5
0.75	16.5	9.45	12.8	4.75	6.95	11.5	14.8
1.0	16.7	9.45	12.7	4.8	7.04	11.8	14.6

*10³ [CAT] (mol dm⁻³) = 2.0 (Ser, Thr, Arg, His and Gln), 4.0 (Gly) and 5.0 (Val); 10³ [A.A] (mol dm⁻³) = 2.0 (Ser, Thr, Arg and His), 6.0 (Gly), 5.0 (Val), 3.0 (Gln); Temp = 303 K (while varying [PTS], D and μ).

TABLE 3—pH VALUES* OF THE REACTION MIXTURES AS [HClO₄] AND [AMINO ACID] VARIED AT 303 K

[HClO ₄] [*] $\times 10^3$ mol dm ⁻³	pH							[A.A] ^{**} $\times 10^3$ mol dm ⁻³	pH		
	Gly	Val	Ser	Thr	Arg	His	Gln		Gly	Val	Thr
1.0	5.48	6.52	5.83	4.36	9.80	7.88	3.85	1.0	3.07	2.51	2.73
2.0	4.98	5.35	3.73	4.00	9.68	7.00	3.55	2.0	3.25	2.79	2.85
4.0	4.35	3.83	3.26	3.62	9.58	6.88	3.24	3.0	3.44	2.92	3.00
5.0	3.95	3.14	3.08	2.85	9.39	6.63	3.08	5.0	3.55	3.14	3.28
8.0	3.53	2.48	2.75	2.68	9.08	6.35	2.91	8.0	3.70	3.54	3.50
10.0	3.38	2.43	2.60	2.58	8.80	6.15	2.83	1.0	3.82	3.75	3.65

*10³ [CAT] (mol dm⁻³) = 2.0 (Ser, Thr, Arg, His and Gln), 4.0 (Gly), 5.0 (Val); 10³ [A.A] (mol dm⁻³) = 2.0 (Ser, Thr, Arg and His), 3.0 (Gln), 5.0 (Val), 6.0 (Gly). **10³ [CAT] (mol dm⁻³) = 2.0 (Thr), 4.0 (Gly), 5.0 (Val); 10³ [HClO₄] (mol dm⁻³) = 5.0.

TABLE 4—ACTIVATION PARAMETERS FOR THE OXIDATION OF AMINO ACIDS BY CAT AT LOW ACID CONCENTRATIONS

Activation parameters	Gly	Val	Ser	Thr	Arg	His	Gln
log A	6.02	6.05	6.01	9.68	15.06	16.86	8.14
E _a (kJ mol ⁻¹)	51.1	52.6	51.7	75.4	105.7	114.9	63.7
ΔH^\ddagger (kJ mol ⁻¹)	46.3	51.1	48.9	72.9	103.4	114.8	60.5
ΔS^\ddagger (JK ⁻¹ mol ⁻¹)	-138.1	-137.3	-138.3	-68.1	93.4	69.4	-97.5
ΔG^\ddagger (kJ mol ⁻¹)	88.1	94.2	90.8	93.5	93.3	93.8	90.0

cationic form, R'CH(NH₃⁺)COOH(SH⁺), in strong acid solutions, which change over to zwitterionic forms, R'CH(NH₃⁺)COO⁻ (S⁺), as the pH of the solution is increased towards isoelectric point and finally to anionic forms, R'CH(NH₂)COO⁻ (S⁻) in strong alkaline solutions (Table 6). Under present

experimental conditions pH > 2.5, it is quite likely that the amino acids exist mostly in the zwitterionic form as the probability of equilibrium,

getting shifted to the left is very low at these [H⁺].

TABLE 5—CONCENTRATIONS (mol dm⁻³) OF VARIOUS SPECIES* PRESENT IN A 0.05 mol dm⁻³ CHLORAMINE-T SOLUTION OVER A RANGE OF pH VALUES

pH	RNCl ⁻	RNHCl	RNCl ₂ =RNH ₂	HOCl	OCl ⁻
0	9.60 × 10 ⁻⁵	4.01 × 10 ⁻³	9.90 × 10 ⁻³	3.95 × 10 ⁻⁷	1.80 × 10 ⁻¹⁴
1	9.60 × 10 ⁻⁴	4.01 × 10 ⁻³	9.90 × 10 ⁻³	3.95 × 10 ⁻⁷	1.80 × 10 ⁻¹³
1.5	—	3.76 × 10 ⁻³	—	—	—
2	7.80 × 10 ⁻³	3.24 × 10 ⁻³	7.98 × 10 ⁻³	3.95 × 10 ⁻⁷	1.80 × 10 ⁻¹²
3	2.83 × 10 ⁻²	1.18 × 10 ⁻²	2.92 × 10 ⁻²	3.95 × 10 ⁻⁷	1.80 × 10 ⁻¹¹
4	3.84 × 10 ⁻²	1.60 × 10 ⁻²	3.95 × 10 ⁻²	3.95 × 10 ⁻⁷	1.80 × 10 ⁻¹⁰
5	4.00 × 10 ⁻²	1.67 × 10 ⁻²	4.10 × 10 ⁻²	3.95 × 10 ⁻⁷	1.80 × 10 ⁻⁹
6	4.00 × 10 ⁻²	1.67 × 10 ⁻²	4.10 × 10 ⁻²	3.95 × 10 ⁻⁷	1.80 × 10 ⁻⁹
7	4.00 × 10 ⁻²	1.67 × 10 ⁻²	4.10 × 10 ⁻²	3.95 × 10 ⁻⁷	1.80 × 10 ⁻⁹
8	4.00 × 10 ⁻²	1.67 × 10 ⁻²	4.10 × 10 ⁻²	3.95 × 10 ⁻⁷	1.80 × 10 ⁻⁹

Values are obtained through first approximation calculations. There are some apparent discrepancies from the point of view of material balance.

One can make a rough estimation of zwitterion concentrations from the measured pH values and isoelectric pH values of amino acids. Under the present experimental conditions, the zwitterion concentration will be around 50–90% of the total amino acid concentrations. Thus at low concentrations as expected and observed in the present investigations, the rate is independent of [S] and [H⁺]. But at larger [H⁺], the equilibrium (8) becomes significant and hence the rate is expected to depend on [S] and [H⁺], *i.e.* the rate would be first order in [S] and inverse first order in [H⁺].

The observed first order in [CAT], zero order in [S] and [H⁺] can be explained through Scheme 1 which involves (i) hydrolysis of RNCl⁻ to HOCl in the rate determining step, (ii) rapid formation of chloro intermediate by the interaction of HOCl and the carboxylate group of amino acid, and (iii) rapid decomposition of the intermediate to the products as shown in Scheme 2.

Scheme 1

The corresponding rate law is

$$-\frac{d[\text{CAT}]}{dt} = k_1[\text{CAT}][\text{H}_2\text{O}] = k_1'[\text{CAT}] \quad (9)$$

$$-\frac{d\ln[\text{CAT}]}{dt} = k_{\text{obs}} = k_1' \quad (10)$$

Addition of the reaction product, PTS had no effect on the rate with all the amino acids, thus indicating the unimportance of the backward reaction of the rate determining step. The observed

TABLE 6—IONISATION CONSTANTS AND pH VALUES AT THE ISOELECTRIC POINTS OF AMINO ACIDS AT 25°

Amino acid	pK ₁	pK ₂	pK ₃	pH ₁ ^a
Gly	2.34	9.60	—	5.97
Val	2.32	9.62	—	5.96
Ser	2.21	9.15	—	5.68
Thr	2.71	9.62	—	6.16
Arg ^b	2.17	9.04	12.48	10.76
His ^b	1.82	6.00	9.17	7.59
Gln	2.17	9.13	—	5.65

^aIsoelectric point (or I.P.); this is the pH at which the maximum number of amino acid molecules are present as zwitterions; for neutral and acidic amino acids pH₁ = (pK₁ + pK₂)/2, for basic amino acids pH₁ = (pK₂ + pK₃)/2. ^bBasic amino acid.

non-influence of the variation of ionic strength of the medium on the rate is also in agreement with Scheme 1. The observed decrease of rate with decrease in dielectric constant of the medium is in accordance with Amis' theory⁷, *i.e.* for the limiting case of zero angle of approach between two dipoles or an ion-dipole system a plot of log *k*_{obs} vs 1/*D* should give a straight line with a negative slope for a reaction between a negative ion and a dipole or between two dipoles. This concept agrees with the present observations where a negative ion and a dipole are involved in the rate-controlling step of Scheme 1. Further, a plot of Δ*H*[‡] vs Δ*S*[‡] was linear with an isokinetic temperature of about 313 K. Δ*G*[‡] values are almost constant indicating the operation of similar mechanism for the reaction of all the amino acids with CAT. A detailed mechanism of oxidation is show in Scheme 2.

References

1. A. K. BOSE, R. M. MEHROTRA and S. P. MUSHRAN, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1973, 11, 896; A. KUMAR, A. K. BOSE and S. P. MUSHRAN, *Monatsch. Chem.*, 1975, 106, 13; J. SHARMA, L. PANDEY and S. P. MUSHRAN, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1980, 19, 475, and references therein.
2. B. T. GOWDA and D. S. MAHADEVAPPA, *J. Chem. Soc., Perkin Trans. 2*, 1983, 823 and references therein.
3. D. S. MAHADEVAPPA, K. S. RANGAPPA, N. M. M. GOWDA and B. T. GOWDA, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1981, 85, 8651, *Int. J. Chem. Kinet.*, 1982, 14, 1183, B. T. GOWDA, B. S. SHERIGARA, D. S. MAHADEVAPPA and K. S. RANGAPPA, *Indian J. Chem., Sect. A*, 1985, 24, 982.
4. E. BISHOP and V. J. JENNINGS, *Talanta*, 1958 1, 197; V. J. JENNINGS, *QC. Crit. Rev. Anal. Chem*, 1974, 407.
5. M. M. CAMPBELL and G. JOHNSON, *J. Chem. Soc., Perkin Trans. 2*, 1978, 78, 65, and references therein.
6. H. D. JAKUBKE and H. JESCHKEIT, "Amino Acids, Peptides and Proteins", Wiley, New York, 1977.
7. E. S. AMIS, "Solvent effects on Reaction Rates and Mechanisms", Academic, New York, 1966.